

SCIENCE AND PHILOSOPHY: A PHILOSOPHY OF CHEMISTRY

DR. KRISHNA KANT SHARMA¹

¹EMAIL: DRKRISHNAKANTSHARMA@GMAIL.COM; M: 9504782781.
ORCID ID: [HTTPS://ORCID.ORG/0000-0001-6009-3024](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6009-3024).

ABSTRACT:

This paper delves into the intersection of philosophy and chemistry, aiming to explore and critique existing chemical theories—ranging from reactions, bonding, and molecular modeling to quantum chemistry—through various philosophical lenses. The study investigates how methodologies from philosophical traditions such as Sankhya, Vaisheshika, Aristotelian thought, and Kantian legacy can be applied to both the education and research of chemistry. This analysis not only enhances the understanding of the underlying assumptions and terminologies in advanced chemical literature but also seeks to position chemistry as an integral branch of philosophy. By addressing issues like demarcation, underdetermination, and falsification within chemical sciences, this research aspires to provide a more unified approach to scientific inquiry, bridging gaps between chemistry, physics, and other disciplines. Ultimately, the study proposes a philosophical framework that could foster a deeper appreciation of chemistry's epistemological and ontological foundations.

Keywords: Science and Philosophy; Philosophy of Chemistry; Chemistry's Epistemological and Ontological Foundations.

This particular research would try to expedite the existing theories of chemical reactions, bonding, molecular modeling, and quantum chemistry amidst the premises of various philosophical foundations. The research would dwell upon the methods of the philosophy and the manner they may be applied to the education and research in chemistry. Moreover, the problems of the *Classical Model* in coping with chemistry would be expedited.

This study will enhance the knowledge, and literature and sustain the central debates in the philosophy of science. The research would promote the understanding of the terminology and concepts presupposed by advanced literature in the area. There would be a new appreciation that would further help establish chemistry as a branch of philosophy.

The research would be based mainly on literature surveys and reviews. The deductive nature of this research would take into account various aspects of the *Sankhya*, *Vaisheshika*, and Aristotelian theories of chemical reaction, molecular modeling, and quantum chemistry. The research would also briefly take into account the legacy of Kant towards the philosophy of Chemistry. The premises leading to the construction of various theories in chemistry would be expedited and their validity may be tested against some established methods of philosophy of science such as demarcation, underdetermination, and falsification. Various fields of science suffer from a great degree of demarcation and segregation that have prevented theorists from reaching appropriate conclusions. The scientific community

suffers from the problem of describing the creation as a natural kind a chemical kind or a physical kind. The methods towards a universal truth should be total and complete, however, we see that different scientists lack a unified approach and most often fail to reach valid conclusions. It is not needed to accept or reject a particular method of physics, chemistry, or any other discipline, however, to make conclusions, it would be needed to integrate all the knowledge of different fields. Three themes can claim to make a unique contribution to the philosophy of science: first, the variety of materials in the (natural and artificial) world; second, extending the world by making *new* stuff; and, third, specific features of the relations between chemistry and physics (Brakel, 2014). Philosophers of science have often been drawn to areas characterized by significant foundational disputes or unclear or ambiguous basic concepts—properties generally not attributed to chemistry (Stuart Rosenfeld, 2000).

Over the last five decades, the *philosophy of chemistry* has made its journey from infancy to maturity, within the philosophy of science. Moreover, there has been a distinct and successful movement from metaphysics to metachemistry. The *philosophy of chemistry* has become a dynamic research field, establishing itself as a sub-discipline of the philosophy of science since the 1990s (Vincent, 2008). The *philosophy of chemistry* considers the methodology and underlying assumptions of the science of chemistry that have been explored by philosophers, chemists, and philosopher-chemist teams (Weisberg, 2001) (McIntyre. L, 1997). However, the philosophy of science due to certain reductions in ideas, chemistry has been reduced to physics and physical sciences (Scerri, 2001). Nevertheless, there has been growing support that chemistry deserves a distinct epistemology. Chemistry is an experimental science that transforms both substances and (chemical) language. On the one hand, chemists analyze and synthesize new compounds in the laboratory; on the other, they make analytical and synthetic statements about these compounds in research articles. It is therefore essential to understand how chemists use their language, what rules govern its use, and what consequences the utilization of this language has for chemistry as a whole (Jacob, 2001). After all, philosophy is an activity of understanding the world, including the sciences. While studying chemistry one needed to strive to learn from the mistakes of the past whereby earlier developments in science education were made separate from advances in the philosophy of science (Sibel, 1999). Chemistry has evolved significantly between the 1st to 21st centuries as it has consecutively evolved from Gas chemistry to Organic Chemistry to Nuclear Chemistry, and finally to Quantum Chemistry in the 21st century (Galloway, 2004). Education and research of chemistry in global terms have to come across various philosophical issues. Philosophy can help chemistry in addressing the issues of Science and Pseudoscience; Conjectures and Refutations; Logic of Discovery or Psychology of Research; Rationality, Objectivity and Values; The Nature and Necessity of Scientific Revolutions; Objectivity, Value Judgment, and Theory Choice; Criteria of Confirmation and Acceptability; Explanation and Prediction; Experimentation and Scientific Realism. For accomplishing all those a firm foundation in understanding the normative, descriptive, ontological, and epistemological boundaries would be needed. It would be further needed to work on ethics in education and research of chemistry.

Chemistry has moved far ahead from the Greek Philosophers and in the 21st century, chemistry has become the largest scientific discipline, producing over half a million publications a year ranging from direct empirical investigations to substantial theoretical work (Weisberg M. N., 2011).

Within the *philosophy of science*, there is already a problem of demarcation between chemistry, physics, and other physical sciences. In addition, there is another problem of demarcation within the

chemical sciences. Chemistry and its various theories over a period have come across the problem of determination leading to a process of steady falsification. Even there are increased demands among the chemical scientific community to re-verify several existing theories of the chemical sciences. Even they suggest new hypotheses against which those theories may be retested and validated. All such emerging voices are not without basis. Further, the chemical sciences also faced the problems of methods, induction, inferences, and realism. It needed to develop the ability to communicate philosophical concepts clearly to understand more advanced issues and arguments in the philosophy of science. It is a challenge for the scientific community to re-establish the nature of the scientific method, theories of confirmation, the demarcation of science from non-science, the rationality of theory change, and scientific realism.

Chemistry has been primarily based upon the synthesis, however, while making analysis problems originate because there has been a difference between analysis and synthesis. Indeed, analysis can provide chemists with some *evidence* about the nature and proportion of the constituents of substances. However, lacking definitive demonstration it may serve the purpose of falsification. There are certain limitations in making conclusions based on synthesis. The chemical proofs depend on the reciprocity of analysis and synthesis, which is at the root of *Immanuel Kant's* admiration for *Georg Ernst Stahl*, who “transformed metals into calx and calx into metals”.

Chemical narratives display meanings, with atoms and molecules in a better way, even if they do not mirror the ultimate reality. Wilhelm Ostwald proposed new narratives of chemical experiments based on the frequency of collisions. Hoffmann has suggested that chemical theories have very weak explanatory power and insisted that two alternative theories, belonging to different paradigms, are not necessarily incommensurable (Roald, 1995). *Linus Pauling's* theory of the chemical bond, associating Lewis's notion of a shared electron pair with the quantum mechanical notion of a covalent wave function, proved to be extremely useful in heuristic terms.

Chemistry, like other experimental sciences, is a normative activity. But if its ruling norm is not to provide the perfect representation of reality, it would be demanded what kind of norms are in use in this science. Experimental scientists like to see their activities as conforming to several criteria or standards, including logical rules, experimental controls, peer review, etc. Conforming to such general widely accepted rules allows them to draw a clear demarcation line between their practices and others that are generally considered to be non-scientific or at least less scientific. The growing number of organic compounds in the nineteenth century nevertheless generated a chaotic situation with dozens of different names for the same substance. Standardization and systematization were the two leading requirements reiterated at the end of the nineteenth century by the first International Conference on Chemical Nomenclature held in Geneva in 1892. Mendeleev's periodic system came to be considered, however, chemists are still unsure about the best way to represent the periodic function.

The philosophy of matter is concerned, physics and chemistry are heirs to two different ancient traditions, with physics deriving from Democritus and Epicurus and chemistry from Empedocles and Aristotle. However, in the Indian context, it still needed to drive something from the Sankhya and Vaishesika in association with Nyaya and Mimamsa.

Aristotle raised the fundamental issue of chemistry, i.e. the generation of new substances out of initial ingredients. This clear recognition of the problem should not, however, be used to suggest that Aristotle conceived a “theory of chemical reaction and chemical substances” (Needham, 1996,

2006). Lavoisier, who came to earn the title of the founder of “modern chemistry”, redefined it as the science that aimed at decomposing natural bodies and “examining separate the various substances entering into their combination” (Laurent, 1789, 1790). Reinforced by John Dalton’s atomic hypothesis, the compositional paradigm has proved very successful. Duhem mainly reproached atomistic explanations for assuming that the properties of a compound could be deduced from those of its constituent elements or atoms (Pierre, 1902, 2002). His criticism also encompassed Lavoisier’s compositional paradigm, since elements are not conserved as such in chemical reactions. Emile Meyerson indirectly addressed the same issue, although, unlike Duhem, he claimed that chemists could not do without atoms (Émile, 1921, 1991).

Because chemists are not concerned with understanding the fine structure of matter, they have regularly dismissed all hypotheses concerning the real existence of atoms. Chemistry may be regarded as a science bound to ontological non-commitment. After quantum chemistry had drawn physics and chemistry into cooperation, chemists continued to debate about the ontological status of relations themselves. If today’s chemists are no longer noncommittal, it is mainly because they assemble atoms and molecules like Lego blocks. They believe in orbits as long as they can explain things with them and design reactions. While chemists do not care for matter, they are by contrast always searching for materials, i.e. substances useful for something also sometimes referred to as ‘agents’. However, chemists are more realists as they believe in the reality of entities, which allows them to operate in the outside world or to be affected by it. “Operational realism” would thus be the right phrase to characterize the chemists’ philosophy.

The chemical sciences are not aimed at unveiling the underlying reality beneath the surface. Instead, they deal with a jungle of molecules and strive to take advantage of their dispositions. Therefore, the philosophy of chemistry may lead chemists or put them under obligation to hunt for revealing truths.

Conclusion:

The exploration of chemistry through a philosophical lens reveals the potential for a more integrated and profound understanding of the discipline. By applying philosophical methods to the analysis of chemical theories, this research underscores the importance of viewing chemistry not merely as an empirical science but as a field rich with philosophical significance. The study highlights the need for a more unified scientific approach that transcends traditional disciplinary boundaries, promoting a holistic understanding of nature. The integration of philosophical perspectives, particularly from Indian and Western traditions, offers a novel appreciation for the complexity and depth of chemical sciences. In conclusion, this research advocates for a renewed consideration of chemistry as a distinct yet interconnected branch of philosophy, essential for advancing both scientific knowledge and philosophical inquiry.

References:

- Brakel, J. v. (2014). Philosophy of Science and Philosophy of Chemistry. *International Journal for Philosophy of Chemistry*, 20, 11-57.
- Émile, M. (1921, 1991). *De l’explication dans les sciences, 2 vols, Paris, Payot; transl., Mary-Alice and A. Sipfle, Explanation in the Sciences*. Dordrecht, Kluwer.
- Galloway, T. (2004). *History of Chemistry*. JFKS.

Intersection of philosophy and chemistry.

Jacob, C. (2001). Interdependent operations in chemical language and practice. *International Journal for Philosophy of Chemistry*, 7 (1), 31-5-

Laurent, L. A. (1789, 1790). *Traité élémentaire de chimie*, Paris, Cuchet; transl., R. Kerr *Elements of Chemistry*. Edinburgh.

McIntyre, L. S. E. (1997). *The case for the philosophy of chemistry*. <http://philsci-archive.pitt.edu/archive/00000254>.

Needham. (1996, 2006). *Aristotle, De generatione et corruptione I.10, 328a13f*.

Pierre, D. (1902, 2002). *Le mixte et la combinaison chimique*, Paris, Fayard, 1985; transl., P. Needham, *Mixture and Chemical Combination and Related Essays*. Dordrecht, Kluwer.

Roald, H. (1995). *The Same and Not the Same*. New York: Columbia University Press.

Scerri, E. R. (2001). The New Philosophy of Chemistry And Its Relevance to Chemical Education. *Chemical Education: Research and Practice in Europe*, 2 (2), 165-170.

Sibel, E. (1999). *Philosophy of Chemistry: An Emerging Field with Implications For Chemistry Education. Paper presented at the History, Philosophy, and Science Teaching Conference*. Pavia, Italy.

Stuart Rosenfeld, N. B. (2000). *Of Minds and Molecules: New Philosophical Perspectives on Chemistry*. Oxford University Press.

Vincent, B. B. (2008). *Philosophy of chemistry* Eds A Brenner, J. Gayon. *French Studies in the Philosophy of Science*. Boston: Springer.

Weisberg, M. (2001). *Why not a philosophy of chemistry?* *American Scientist*.

Weisberg, M. N. (2011). *Philosophy of Chemistry*, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2016 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (Ed. Stanford: <https://plato.stanford.edu/cgi-bin/encyclopedia/archinfo.cgi?entry=chemistry>).
